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Impacts and Value Chains of the Cloud-Edge-IoT Continuum in the Agricultural Sector

Why is the CEI continuum important for the Agricultural Sector?

With regards to employment and revenue, the agriculture sector is comparatively small. But it has a strategic importance and criticality for Europe to secure food supply. Agriculture is the industry with lowest levels of adoption of CEI technologies compared to the other considered sectors namely Energy & Utilities, Healthcare, Manufacturing and Mobility & Logistics.

Cloud computing:

26% Extensive use

34% Limited use

21% Plan to use

Edge:

0% Extensive use

14% Limited use

31% Plan to use

IoT:

3% Extensive use

34% Limited use

31% Plan to use

As part of its efforts to promote the CEI Continuum, the EUCEI initiative has carried out a series of industry focused surveys on current and planned adoptions. The rate of success of CEI projects in agriculture is lower than the average of the other sectors and concerns regarding network unreliability are particularly common in this sector. However, even in agriculture, more than four out of five respondents expect to be using cloud in the near future. Cloud adoption is now quite widespread and a normal part of IT strategies. Thus, agriculture lags in adoption of cloud for IoT, but the sector expects to narrow the gap over time.

What are the main opportunities for CEI in Agriculture?

Remote Asset Tracking and Monitoring (esp. animal tagging): Managing the farm assets around the whole farm is challenging. CEI technology, esp. cloud solutions with modest requirements on data and latency, are a vital part of the remote locating and monitoring of equipment and of livestock. This leads to improved animal welfare, higher efficiency of machinery and condition monitoring for both animals and machinery.

Precision Agriculture: The varying environmental conditions are challenging for production processes. In this context, precision agriculture strives for higher yields of crops and / or reduce used resources e.g. water, energy and pesticides. The applications utilize collected data on the field and crop to control and adjust automated solutions based on the local specifics. Typically, applications combine cloud solutions with edge computing for on-device automation and use distributed data collection for field monitoring.

Another promising application area is the autonomous weeding, since it combines precision agriculture with automation.

Agricultural Equipment Automation: A fully autonomous agricultural equipment will considerably reduce human labor and support farmers in the future. The expected results are higher yield, lower labour costs, remote operation and both higher profitability, quality and sustainability. The autonomous systems are based on CEI technologies and Artificial Intelligence (AI) is key to improve precision and enable machines to make intelligent decisions despite complexity. On-board automation systems are on the edge, but usually combined with cloud solutions for management and updating purposes.

What are the data, value and information flows in Manufacturing?

The main actors in the value chain are the farmers, which apply the CEI solutions in their work processes, and the equipment manufacturers, who manufacture, sell and provide life cycle support for agricultural machinery. Therefore, they are in the center of the figure.

CEI technologies are mainly integrated in farm equipment, making the equipment manufacturer essential for the uptake of CEI in agriculture. The machines are therefore hybrid service bundles: physical products combined with support, software and the fitting data-based services. The equipment manufacturers are making the decisions on choosing and procuring concrete technologies and applications, keeping the farmers requirements in mind and also managing the supply chain. This includes providers for hardware, software and infrastructure elements for the CEI solution.

In Agriculture, the OEMs and other manufacturers of agricultural machinery are the active designer of most CEI applications in agriculture. The integration of CEI technologies is the next step in digitalization of agricultural machinery, striving for higher precision and automation. The farmers are customers and users of the machines including the integrated software and hardware solutions, thus the actual demand side with user requirements.

One challenge for farmers is to maintain their data sovereignty, partly because many manufacturers use proprietary data formats. This may contribute to vendor lock-ins because of proprietary systems and data formats. Therefore, the value chain includes the data exchange via API provided by an additional actor ("Intermediary"). These take on the challenge of vendor-independent data exchange and management. In addition, there are other software providers besides the manufacturers of the agricultural machinery, including small regional players. To enable farmers to use these systems with minimal effort, standardized data exchange formats and processes are a pressing topic in the industry.

What are the key service requirements for the agricultural sector?

For agricultural CEI-applications, the main priority is overall cost-effectiveness, as the machines are long-term investments with tight calculations for farmers. Additionally, the machines have to be internationally applicable, available 24/7 and particularly robust against environmental influences, as agricultural machinery is used for decades. They have to cover both offline applicability and updateability, despite common unreliability of networks, while following cyber security norms, AI norms and standards at all times. The topics of interoperability for seamless data exchange and interconnectivity of machinery and cloud systems are also of increasing importance.

Design and Installation

- ☁ Selection of CEI technologies based on cost efficiency and user experience, e.g. the seamless integration in the IT-system of the agricultural machinery and existing software such as Farm Management Information Systems
- ☁ Solutions should be customized to specifics of the farm, such as the environmental conditions on the field, the range of crops and processes
- ☁ AI-supported machinery must fit the (upcoming) norms and certification requirements regarding data collection and processing
- ☁ Training farmers, their staff and contractors is essential in the purchasing process, also including the supporting actors such as consulting agencies (see value chain).

Operation

- ☁ The system must operate in near-real-time on the field, even with unreliable network conditions, which requires edge solutions. Later on, updates can be done via cloud, resulting into currently low latency and availability requirements on OEM clouds.
- ☁ The exchange of all collected data (agronomic and telemetric) is required to be seamless and standardized. Currently, a lot of proprietary data formats are used, subsequently there is a lack of interoperability.
- ☁ The machine manufacturer ensures product liability, which results into the need of strict cyber security and a closed system to secure it against tampering with the technical system.
- ☁ A user-friendly interface is essential for farmers and their contractors.

Maintenance and Upgrade

- ☁ The long lifecycle of agricultural machinery demands upgrades to ensure full operability for several decades and fit future requirements (e.g. changing regulations for fertilizers)
- ☁ Service personnel should be able to perform the maintenance and updates on-site and ensure high availability of the system (up to 24/7). The software updates will increase with CEI applications, therefore a digital updatability via cloud (using WiFi or mobile 5G network) is key.
- ☁ To ensure the needed availability and compatibility with software systems, versioning of software and sometimes allowing the use of older versions for compatibility purposes is required.

What are the value chain catalysts for CEI adoption?

1. Collaborate with Expert Providers

Partner with CEI service providers, R&D, and technology experts to bridge expertise gaps and facilitate communication with other technology providers, leveraging their knowledge to streamline CEI customization and integration efforts.

2. Empower Domain Experts

Involve domain experts whose workflows are affected by CEI systems as key decision makers. Design CEI solutions to support and assist domain experts, capturing their valuable knowledge and addressing skill gaps.

3. Innovate for Future Readiness

Exploit CEI solutions as drivers of innovation and competitive advantage, helping the sector prepare for upcoming market changes. Explore collaborative data-sharing applications along the supply chain to unlock additional value and partnerships.

If you're interested in growth opportunities in this sector or want to learn more, contact us at: info@eucloudedgeiot.eu